
Mathematical Model of Size Penetration into the Yarn in the Warp Sizing

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Abstract: This study discusses the capillary model of the space formed between the fibers in the yarn. Transfer of solution into yarn is one of the important factors affecting the processes and in application of textiles. The solution that flows into the space between fibers can cause changes in dimensions which have a direct effect on the structure of space between fibers in the yarn. Furthermore, in this study, an analysis of the geometry model of fiber bonds in the yarn suggested by Schwartz was used to determine the capillary diameter of the yarn and in the determining the area. This study also considered the nature of fibers which are swelling while absorbing water molecules. The results of the discussion of this model were used to understand the effects of geometric parameters and materials in fluid transfer in the application of warp sizing using Poisson law. The theoretical calculation resulted differently compared to the results of research on cotton yarn which are assumed to be that the fibers are considered perfectly round, uniform twist. The absence of fiber migration greatly affects the cavity between fibers in the yarn. In addition, other problems were found in the covenant process such as viscosity stability during the process, as well as the quality of the size recipe used.

Keywords: capillary, geometry, swelling, viscosity

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1. Introduction

The main target of the warp sizing is to produce yarns with high weaving power. This needs to be supported with the selection of size recipes according to the type of yarn that will be sized to be made into warp yarns. Furthermore, in order to fulfill the main target, the warp sizing is expected to coat the yarn not only with the size which is resistant to abrasion, but also with the size which drips into the yarn, and the amount of size penetration should not be excessive which can cause the warp to stiffen and lose its flexibility. The viscosity of size solution will affect the coating and penetration of size into the yarn. Low viscosity will result in more penetrated size in the yarn and the film layer on the surface of the yarn is not formed.

The size absorption by the yarns in the warp sizing depends on the space between the fibers present in the yarn, the viscosity of size, the pressure of the roller immersion and the squeezer roller. The size absorbed in this case is that which coats (forms film) the surface of the yarn and which is penetrated (absorbed) into the yarn. Besides, the transfer of size solution into the space between fibers will cause the fibers in the yarn to swell and this will result in changes in the spatial structure between fibers. This research focused on the theoretical study of inter-fiber space in yarns related to absorption in the warp sizing, which was then compared to the results of investigations taking into account the size that coated the surface of the yarn.

From this description, this research is intended to empirically test the mathematical model of yarn size absorption in the warp sizing as a weaving preparation process.

2. Estimated Model of Size Absorption in Yarns

2.1. Space between Fibers in Yarn

The space between fibers is ideally a triangular arc, and this space will be filled with liquid. If p is the circumference formed by the three sides of the fiber cross section which are tangent to each other as shown in Figure 1, then

$$p = 3 \frac{2\pi r}{6}$$

atau

$$p = \pi r \tag{1}$$

As shown in Figure 1, the length of each side of the arc which forms the space between fibers is the same as that $\frac{1}{6}$ of the circumference of a fiber cross section. This can be related to mass per unit length, μ , from fiber (fineness), and fiber density, ρ , then

$$\mu = \pi r^2 \rho$$

or

$$r^2 = \frac{\mu}{\pi \rho} \tag{2}$$

so equation (1) becomes

$$p = \sqrt{\frac{\pi \mu}{\rho}} \tag{3}$$

Because it is very small, the space between fibers is considered as a circle so that the diameter of the space between fibers is,

$$\phi = \frac{p}{\pi} \tag{4}$$

Figure 1. Inter fiber space in closed packing configuration [1]

The substitution of p with equation (3) is obtained by

$$\phi = \frac{1}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\pi \mu}{\rho}} \quad (5)$$

or

$$\phi = \sqrt{\frac{\pi \mu}{\pi^2 \rho}} \quad (6)$$

so obtained

$$\phi = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\pi \rho}} \quad (7)$$

2.2. Penetration of size into yarn

The sizing begins with wetting. This is not done only on the surface of the yarn, but needs to penetrate into the yarn through the pores or space between fibers in the yarn.

The relationship between the amount of solution flowing per unit time, V , and the difference in pressure, ΔP , diameter of space between fibers, ϕ , solution viscosity η , and the length of inter fiber space, l , if following Poisson law as follows [2], [3]:

$$V = \frac{\Delta P \phi^2}{8 \eta l} \quad (8)$$

Figure 2. Warp sizing process

And if Q is a notation of the amount of solution absorbed, and t is a notation from the time the yarn is submerged in solution, then the relationship mentioned above will become

$$Q = \frac{\Delta P \phi^2 t}{8 \eta l} \quad (9)$$

From equation (4) it can be seen that the penetration of size solution into yarn is proportional to roller pressure, diameter between fibers and immersion time, and inversely proportional to the viscosity of the solution.

Next is the substitution of ϕ in equation (9) above with equation (7)

$$Q = \frac{\Delta P t}{8 \eta l} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\pi \rho}} \right)^2 \tag{10}$$

then acquired

$$Q = \frac{\Delta P \mu t}{8 \eta \pi \rho l} \tag{11}$$

Figure 3. Size box

Cotton fibers consist almost entirely of cellulose which has an empirical formula $(C_6H_{10}O_5)_n$, where n is the degree of polarity depending on the size of the molecule. In the absorption process, there is an interaction between water molecules and fiber molecules. all natural fibers have hydroxyl groups in each of their remaining glucos, and hydrogen bonds can form between these water molecules and hydroxyl groups.

Figure 4. Absorption of water molecules by cellulose molecular hydroxyl groups [1]

The molecular weight of the water is 18 and the molecular weight of the remaining glucose is 162, so if the water molecule joins each hydroxyl group, then the mass of the molecule will increase by 33%. In fact, not all hydroxyl groups absorb water because of the crystalline region which tends to remain unchanged. This area is around the area [1], but the fact shows that the absorption of the water molecules that first joins the hydroxyl group can be followed by the second molecule. In other words, the water molecules can form layers, the first layer by the first water molecule, and the next layer by the next water molecule, as shown in Figure 5.

The bond of water molecules is directly formed stronger on the molecular structure, while the bonds will indirectly be easily released. The arrangement is erratic, but not as free as liquid water molecules, or ice-shaped water molecules.

The fineness or roughness of a fiber is sometimes determined by its diameter, but in industry or research, the diameter of a fiber is part of the characteristics of various dimensions. Other sizes such as cross-sectional areas that indicate the type of fiber to be compared with weight per unit length in a cross section . The cross-sectional area can be calculated from the density (g/cm^3), or its linear density ($\text{g/cm} \cdot 10^{-8}$). Other sizes such as wall thickness are a measurement used to describe cavities from fibers that are related to the maturity of a fiber. As with yarn numbering, fiber fineness is defined as mass per unit length, so the size of the fineness of this fiber will determine the amount of fiber in the cross section of the yarn [5].

When fiber absorbs water molecules, there will be a swelling of fibers, so that the structure of the yarn will change as shown in Figure 6 [1],

Figure 5. Absorption of fiber molecules [1]

Figure 6. Cross section of dry and wet fibers

Thus, equation (3) needs to be revised in accordance with the fiber used for the warp sizing. For example, if the size is made of cotton fiber as in this study, the size penetration into the yarn is formulated as equation (11) becomes

$$Q = 1,2 \frac{\Delta P \mu t}{8 \eta \pi \rho l} \tag{12}$$

or

$$Q = 0,15 \frac{\Delta P \mu t}{\eta \pi \rho l} \tag{13}$$

because the swelling diameter of cotton fiber is 20% [1], so it is multiplied by 1.2.

2.3. The Number space between fibers in the yarn

Equation (5) applies only to one space between fibers in the yarn, whereas the number space between fibers depends on the number fiber in the yarn, Table 1 shows the relationship between the number fiber in the yarn and the number space between fibers in the yarn.

Table 1. Total Inter-Fiber Space in yarn close packing structure [1]

Layer	Layers number	Number fiber	Number layer/interfiber space	Total interfiber space
1	1	1	0	0
2	6	7	6	6
3	12	19	18	24
4	18	37	30	54
5	24	61	42	96
6	30	91	54	150
7	36	127	66	216
8	42	169	78	294
9	48	217	90	384
10	54	271	102	486

2.4. Size filmed on the surface of the yarn

In the warp sizing, size not only seeps or drips into the yarn but also coats the surface of the yarn. According to Hoshiyama [4] the relationship between the size lining the yarn and penetrating into the space between fibers depends on the viscosity of the solution, high viscosity will result in decreased size penetration into the yarn. The relationship can be shown in Figure 7. From the graph Figure 7 shows that coating the size solution onto the yarn surface tends to increase in proportion to the increase in viscosity of the size solution, while penetration of the size solution into the yarn tends to decrease when the viscosity of size solution increases. Thus it can be understood that the thickness of a size solution will make it difficult to penetrate into the yarn. Therefore, the warp sizing with a high viscosity of size solution will further strengthen the coating of size on the surface of the yarn.

Figure 7. Relationship between viscosity and size percentage [4]

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Material studied

The material studied was cotton yarn with specifications: Ne₁₃₀ with 22 tpi and 15% unevenness, Ne₁₄₀ with 25 tpi and unevenness 14%, Ne₁₅₀ with 28 tpi and unevenness 13%, then Ne₁₆₀ with 31 tpi and unevenness 12%. The size specifications can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Specifications for sizing process

Item	Ne ₁₃₀	Ne ₁₄₀	Ne ₁₅₀	Ne ₁₆₀
Speed	25 m/menit	25 m/menit	25 m/menit	25 m/menit
Squeez roll	300 kg/cm ²	300 kg/cm ²	300 kg/cm ²	300 kg/cm ²
Twist	8,8/cm	10/cm	11/cm	12,4/cm
Warp density	26/cm	34/cm	36/cm	38/cm
Warp Number	3400	4500	4765	4850
Viscosity	100 cps	100 cps	100 cps	100 cps
Draft	1%	1%	1%	1%
Regain	14%	14%	14%	14%

3.4. Size recipe

Tapioca size is the main ingredient in the size recipe used in this study. The size recipe used in this study is that every 1 (one) liter of water is 121 grams of size, with details as follow:

- Tapioka: 70 g
- PVA: 30 g
- Solgum: 6 g
- Tylose: 8 g
- Solvilwax: 7 g

3.5. Research procedure

The samples of warp yarn before sizing, for each count, namely Ne₁30, Ne₁40, Ne₁50 and Ne₁60 were taken from the warp machine, with the change of warp beam of 1 (one) meter, and then weighed and then divided by the number of yarns.

While samples for warp yarns after sizing, for each count were taken from the sizing machine, with the weaving beam changes as long as 1 (one) meter, then weighed and then divided by the number of yarns.

The weight difference per yarn from the results of weighing the sample between warp yarns before sized with warp yarns after sizing was referred as the size content in the yarn absorbed during the warp sizing process.

4. Results and discussion

The steps to get the theoretical results of the size absorbed in the yarn are to calculate the number of fiber in the yarn is $15000/(Ne_1 \cdot \mu)$ [5]. Based on the configuration of the close-packing structure tabulated in Table 1, the interpolation calculation Lagrange interpolation [7] used Microsoft Office Excel 2007 Software program. in this calculation the number of inter-fiber space was obtained Ne₁30 = 228, Ne₁40 = 176, Ne₁50 = 141, and Ne₁60 = 114.

The relationship between size coated and penetrated in graph 7 is the relationship between viscosity and size percentage of Hoshiyama [4], then size penetrated into yarn in this study which used 100 cps viscosity, was around 35%. Thus for Ne₁30, the size penetrated is 35% from 14% equal to 4.9%. For Ne₁40, the size penetrated is 3.76%, while for Ne₁50, the size penetrated is 3.61% and size Ne₁60 penetrated is 3.45 %. The size absorbed from the results of the investigation was obtained as: Ne₁30 size absorbed was 14.10% and standard deviation of 1.30%, Ne₁40 size absorbed was 13.60% and standard deviation of 0.67%, Ne₁50 size absorbed was 13.30% and the standard deviation of 0.60% and the size absorbed Ne₁60 is 13.05% and the standard deviation is 1.30%.

These results showed that the calculation of size penetration into yarn is lower compared to the results of the investigation. The average calculation result was 2.285% lower than the results of the investigation or the difference is almost a quarter. Furthermore, it can also be seen that only the yarn number Ne₁30 has the same theoretical results compared to the results of the investigation. The results of theoretical calculations in succession between the numbers Ne₁30 and Ne₁40 was 3.27%; between numbers Ne₁40 and Ne₁50 was 0.42%, between numbers Ne₁50 and Ne₁60 was 0.44. The difference between the results of theoretical calculations shows inconsistency, even though the fineness of the fibers used and the hardness of yarns or twist factors are the same. The results of successive investigations between the numbers Ne₁30 and Ne₁40 was 0.5%; between numbers Ne₁40 and Ne₁50 was 0.3%, between numbers Ne₁50 and Ne₁60 was 0.25, the difference between the results of this investigation also showed inconsistency. Inconsistency or the difference in the value from theoretical and investigative calculations in this study may be because many factors are considered ideal. Though the fiber is considered to be perfectly round, uniform twist, lack of fiber migration, all of which greatly affect the cavity between fibers in the yarn . Besides, the problem is in the covenant process such as viscosity stability during the process, as well as the quality of the size recipe used. The results of the regression analysis using Microsoft Office Excel 2007 Software for calculations were $y = -0,00045 x + 0.05955$ with $r^2 = 0.88$ while from the investigation, $y = -0,000074 x + 0,05098$ with $r^2 = 0,80$. When plotted into the result graph as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Linear regression for the results of theoretical calculations and investigation of size penetration into the yarn

From the regression, the equation obtained with 88% correlation coefficient for theoretical calculations and 80% correlation coefficients for the results of investigations. Many factors are considered ideal such as assuming that fiber is considered to be perfectly round [8], uniform twist [2, 1], lack of migration of fibers [1]. This is very affecting the cavity between fibers in the yarn. Additional problems were found in the covenant process such as viscosity stability [5] during the process, as well as the quality of the size recipe [8] used, the process, as well as the quality of the starch recipe [8] used.

5. Conclusions

With the assumptions that the fibers in the cylindrical yarn are perfect, the bonding of fibers in the cross section of the yarn forms a hexagonal configuration following Schwartz's theory. Uniform yarn twist, viscosity of the solution during stable condition, fiber swelling due to absorption of water molecules, drafts that occur in rolling into the warp beam, and regain, the calculation of size absorption by warp yarn was theoretically lower than the results of the study. The results of regression analysis of equations obtained with high coefficients do not show the same or parallel slope. Thus the mathematical model built cannot be used to estimate the size penetrated into the yarn.

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